

FLEXURAL FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF ARAMID REINFORCED ALUMINUM
7075 LAMINATE (ARALL-I) AND AL 7075 ALLOY SHEET
IN AIR AND IN SALT LADENED HUMID AIR

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- ABSTRACT

Fatigue and corrosion fatigue studies were conducted in flexure on aramid reinforced aluminum laminate (ARALL-I) in lab and salt ladened moist air. The ARALL results are compared to data for Al 7075-T6 and Al 7075-T73 alloy sheet. In lab air, the ARALL-I showed enhanced fatigue endurance behavior and at 10^7 cycles to failure, an improvement in stress carrying ability of 12 ksi (83 MPa) is achieved. In the salt contaminated, moist air environment, the ARALL-I showed about 15 ksi (103 MPa) improvement in load carrying capability in the low cycle fatigue range, whereas in high cycle fatigue, the enhanced fatigue behavior of the ARALL-I is somewhat less. Micro and macro examination of the fatigued specimens showed that the outer laminates of the ARALL cracked early in the fatigue life and eventually delaminated. Damage of the fibers was not observed until near the end of the fatigue life. When flexed in a direction transverse to the direction of the fibers, the fatigue life was dominated by fatigue of the 7075 Al laminate sheets.

INTRODUCTION

In order to meet the future needs of aircraft design and to compete with graphite epoxy composites in weight savings, the aluminum industry is developing numerous alloys and composites [1]. One such category of

composites are aramid reinforced aluminum laminates (ARALL) which were initially developed at the University of Delft, Netherlands [2]. ARALL is a laminate of thin sheets of aluminum, typically 0.011 to 0.016 inches (0.28 to 0.406 mm) thick, and aramid fibers, typically 0.008 (0.203 mm) inches thick in a prepreg, adhesively bonded together to form a laminate. ARALL with two plies of Enka unidirectional aramid fibers impregnated with 3M Company AF-163-2, 250°F cured adhesive and three plies of chromic acid anodized Al 7075-T6 sheet layers is designated as ARALL-I. The advantages of ARALL are that the aluminum sheet provides isotropic shear and compressive strengths, while the laminate is fatigue crack resistant in tension dominated fatigue [3]. ARALL also provides a density advantage over monolithic aluminum sheet and demonstrates a greater mechanical damping capacity relative to aluminum sheet [4].

In this paper, the flexural fatigue characteristics are reported for ARALL-I laminated composites in laboratory air and in humid salt laden humid air. This latter environment simulates a condensed sea coast dew. Results of reinforced material are presented and compared with those of sheet Al 7075-T6 and 7075-T73 alloy. SEM fractography was also performed to gain information about the mechanism of fatigue fracture.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Three sheets of ARALL-I sheet materials were obtained from ALCOA Corporation ALCOA Center, Pennsylvania. Two of the sheets were painted with primer while the third sheet was provided unpainted. The unpainted sheet was used for the corrosion fatigue tests. Al 7075-T6 sheet material was heat treated to the T73 temper to provide material in the stress corrosion cracking resistant condition for comparisons. Tensile tests were performed on the sheet materials. Results are tabulated in Table I. The microstructure of the ARALL-I material is shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I
MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ARALL-I and Al 7075 SHEET

<u>Material</u>	<u>Orientation</u>	<u>E (Msi)</u>	<u>TYS (ksi)</u>	<u>UTS (ksi)</u>
Al 7075-T6	L	10.4	72.6	82.0
Al 7075-T73	L	10.4	70.0	75.0
ARALL-I	L	9.9	-	117.0
ARALL-I	T	7.5	48.0	59.0

Figure 1. Microstructure of ARALL-I

The tensile tests show that the longitudinal ARALL-I did not exhibit a definite tensile yield stress (TYS), but had an ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of 117 ksi (807 MPa) which is higher than Al 7075 in both T6 and T73 tempers. The tensile yield and ultimate strengths for the transverse orientation of 48 and 59 ksi (331 and 407 MPa), respectively are, however, less than for the Al 7075 sheet in either temper.

Two Sonntag SF-2-U bending fatigue machines (Wiedemann Division of Warner and Swasey Company) were used for fatigue testing at 30 Hz. The procedures used were the same as those in studies of flexural fatigue and corrosion fatigue of 7075-T73 and SiC/Al metal matrix composites [5, 6] except that the edges of the ARALL-I were sealed with epoxy to prevent moisture egress into the polymers of the laminate in the corrosion fatigue tests. The initial alternating load (constant amplitude) was applied using an off-center weight in which the eccentric distance could be increased to increase the load. Only purely alternating bending loads were used for these tests ($R = -1$).

Samples fatigued in air were tested after machining and cleaning. Samples fatigued in salt, moist air were cleaned, dipped in an aqueous 3.5 w/o NaCl solution, dried to form a thin salt contamination layer, and then placed in an environmental chamber on the fatigue machine at

95 percent relative humidity. The specimens were conditioned approximately 1/2 hour before testing to allow time for the NaCl crystals to absorb their natural amount of moisture, thereby forming the corrodent.

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the flexural fatigue behavior of ARALL-I with longitudinally oriented fibers compared with the flexural fatigue behavior of Al 7075 alloy in both the strong T6 temper and the stress corrosion cracking resistant temper, T73. The ARALL-I demonstrates a significant improvement in fatigue resistance at all stress levels. It is noted that the unpainted ARALL-I plates demonstrated a higher resistance to fatigue than did the painted ARALL-I plates. It is also noted that the fatigue curves of the ARALL-I are semilogarithmically linear in the range 10^4 to 10^7 cycles to failure whereas the aluminum alloy curves follow the normal convex shape of metals. This linear behavior in the ARALL-I laminate is typical of metal matrix composites such as graphite-aluminum and silicon carbide-aluminum [7].

Flexure fatigue curves for ARALL-I in lab air with longitudinally and transversely oriented fibers are shown in Figure 3. As expected due to the unidirectional aramid fiber prepreg, the fatigue resistance in the material with fibers oriented longitudinally to the direction of loading is considerably better than the fatigue resistance when the fibers are oriented transverse to the loading direction. In contrast to the linear behavior of the longitudinally oriented material, the transversely oriented material shows the convex shape of metals. Since there are no transverse plied fibers in the ARALL-I, a calculated area-compensated endurance limit curve is also shown in the Figure 3. This calculated curve adjusts the loading cross section assuming that the entire transverse load is carried in the aluminum plies, with no contribution from the polymer plies. As can be seen by comparison, the area-compensated curve reproduces the Al 7075-T6 curve shown in Figure 2.

The flexural corrosion fatigue behavior of the ARALL-I, Al 7075-T6, and Al 7075-T73 in salt contaminated, moist air is shown in Figure 4. The corrosive environment degrades the fatigue resistance of all the materials tested by approximately one order of magnitude. The fatigue resistance of the ARALL-I, however, remains superior to that of the Al alloy, with a near constant 12 ksi (83 MPa) improvement in load carrying ability.

Figure 2. Flexural fatigue (R=-1) of ARALL-I, Al 7075-T6, and Al 7075-T73 in air

Figure 3. Flexural fatigue (R=-1) of ARALL-I comparing laminate behavior with fiber orientation

Figure 4. Corrosion fatigue of ARALL-I and 7075 Al sheet materials in salt contaminated, moist air

Examination of the fatigue specimens optically and by scanning electron microscopy showed that the outer aluminum laminates cracked and delaminated during the fatigue. Figure 5 shows representative fractographs. Damage to the fibers was not in evidence until near the end of the fatigue life. Fractography results of transverse specimens showed that the fatigue life was dominated by fatigue in the matrix.

Figure 5. Fracture surfaces of ARALL-I following flexure fatigue

SUMMARY

The flexural fatigue and corrosion fatigue behavior of ARALL-I have been studied and compared with Al 7075-T6 and 7075-T73 sheet materials. Results show that a substantial improvement in fatigue endurance is achieved in the ARALL-I when flexure is longitudinal to the fiber orientation. In transversely oriented specimens, fatigue characteristics are dominated by fatigue in the metal laminates and ARALL-I fatigue curves are the same as the Al 7075-T6 alloy when cross section stress is adjusted by calculating stress based on metal area cross section. Fractography results show that the laminate fails by cracking in the outer laminates, followed by debonding at the metal/polymer interface.

REFERENCES

1. Holt, D.J., Aluminum: The Next Decade, Aerospace Engineering, September/October, 1984, pp. 62-67.
2. Marissen, R. and Vogelesang, L.B., Development of a New Hybrid Material: ARALL, presented at Intercontinental SAMPE Meeting, Cannes, France, January, 1981.
3. Bucci, R.J., Mueller, L.N. Schultz, R.W., and Prohaska, J.L., Results from a Cooperative Test Program on ARALL, Aramid Aluminum Laminate, SAMPE, Anaheim, California, April 6-9, 1987.
4. Nutter, N. and Gray, R.A., Unpublished NRL research.
5. Funke, A.T., Hasson, D.F., and Crowe, C.R., Corrosion Fatigue of Anodized Aluminum 7075-T73 in Salt Ladened Humid Air, U.S. Naval Academy, Report EW-1-81, January 1981, AD A103152.
6. Hasson, D.F., Crowe, C.R. Ahearn, J.S., and Cooke, D.C., Fatigue and Corrosion Fatigue of SiC/Al Metal Matrix Composites in Failure Mechanisms in High Performance Materials, ed. Early, J.G., Shives, T.R. and Smith, J.H., Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, MA, 1985, pp. 147-156.
7. Crowe, C.R., Fatigue and Corrosion Fatigue of Metal Matrix Composites, in Proc. Sixth Metal Matrix Composites Technology Conference, MMCTC - Kaman Tempo, Santa Barbara, CA, 1985, pp. 19-1 to 19-13.

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